

data are presented in Table 1. All the compounds, in general, exhibited the following ir bands : 820–830 (C₂N₃), 1 280–1 275 (C–O–C), 1 670–1 690 (NH–C), 1 150–1 175 (C–O) and 1 310–1 350 (C–N).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition (mm) ^a			M. t ^{**}
				<i>E. c.</i>	<i>S. a.</i>	<i>K.</i>	
1.	Aniline	240	71	1.5	0.5	1.0	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	252	72	0.5	0.0	0.0	+
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	240	69	2.5	0.5	2.0	+
4.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	245	76	2.0	2.5	1.0	+
5.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	232	68	1.5	2.0	1.0	0
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	220	72	0.5	0.0	0.5	+
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	168	78	1.0	0.5	0.5	+
8.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	226	67	3.0	2.0	0.5	0
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	200	69	1.5	2.0	2.5	+
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	273	78	1.5	2.5	1.0	+

^a *E. c.* = *E. coli*, *S. a.* = *S. aureus*, *K.* = *Klebsiella*,

^{**} *M. t.* = *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇RV; (+) = positive.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-5-triazines

K. R. DESAI* and B. D. MISTRY

Department of Chemistry,
South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

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s-Triazine¹ nucleus has been the subject of several investigations in order to study its potential as antibacterial agent. Sulphonamides form a separate group among the antibacterials. Furthermore, since a number of thiourea derivatives are reported to possess biological activities², it was anticipated that the combined presence of N–C=S and sulphanilamido groupings in a *s*-triazine ring may enhance

antibacterial activity³. Hence the title *s*-triazine derivatives (1a–j) were synthesised to study their potentiality as antibacterial agents.

Cyanuric chloride and *p*-anisidine were condensed in equimolar proportions. The resultant product was reacted with sulphamethoxypyridazine followed by reaction with arylthiourea to yield the corresponding 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazines. Structures of the compounds were established by elemental and spectral data (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0–5°, a solution of *p*-anisidine (1.23 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added and neutral pH was maintained. The stirring was continued at the same temperature (0–5°) for 2 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 150°.

2-(4'-Methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (2.71 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, a solution of sulphamethoxypyridazine (2.80 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added dropwise for 0.5 h and neutral pH was maintained. The temperature was then gradually raised to 45° during 2 h. The solution was then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (78%), m.p. > 300°.

General procedure for preparation of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine: A mixture of 2-(4'-methoxyanilino)-4-[N⁴-(N¹-(6'-methoxy-3'-pyridazinyl)sulphanilamido)]-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (5.15 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol; $\nu_{\max}$ 820, 1 410 (C₂N₃), 1 500 (thiourea C–N), 1 240 (C–O–C), 1 135 (S–O) and 1 550–1 560 cm⁻¹ (sec. amine NH).

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1a–j

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C.	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
1a	C ₆ H ₅	158	62	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.10 (58.81)	4.18 (4.15)	22.15 (22.21)
1b	<i>o</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	151	61	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.99 (54.01)	4.85 (4.87)	21.69 (21.72)
1c	<i>m</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	124	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.98 (54.01)	4.86 (4.87)	21.61 (21.72)
1d	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	64	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.97 (54.01)	4.82 (4.87)	21.67 (21.72)
1e	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	152	59	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.80 (50.54)	3.82 (3.78)	21.02 (21.05)
1f	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	182	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.45 (50.54)	3.76 (3.78)	20.96 (21.05)
1g	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	185	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.14 (50.54)	3.88 (3.78)	20.99 (21.05)
1h	<i>o</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	158	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₁₁ S ₂	49.68 (49.76)	3.75 (3.72)	22.88 (22.80)
1i	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	167	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	52.41 (52.70)	4.80 (4.27)	21.12 (21.20)
1j	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180	81	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	52.40 (52.70)	4.26 (4.27)	21.11 (21.20)

Biological screening : The antibacterial activity of **1** was determined against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ of acetone following the agar plate method⁵. Amongst the compounds tested, **1b** was found to exhibit relatively higher activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 1.5 and 1.0 mm, respectively), **1h** was more active against *S. aureus* than *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 1.0 and 0.5 mm, respectively), and **1e** was inactive against *S. aureus* but it caused the inhibition of *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 1.0 mm). Minimum activity was found in **1a** and **1j** (zone of inhibition for both types of bacteria being same, i.e. 0.5 mm).

All the compounds tested show practically very poor activity compared to the activity of sulphamethoxypyridazine against bacteria, which further proves that *N*⁴-substitution of sulphonamide does not prove advantageous according to PABA mechanism. The little activity in spite of this can be attributed to *p*-methoxyanilino and arylthioureido moieties.

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

K. P. RODA, R. N. VANSADIA and HANSA PAREKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005

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1, 3,4-Oxadiazoles are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties¹. Thymol derivatives have also been reported to possess physiological properties². Keeping this in view, some new 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles bearing thymol moiety of type **4** have been synthesised (Scheme 1).

Thymol was condensed with chloroacetic acid and esterified (**1**) which was treated with hydrazine hydrate to get the hydrazide (**2**). The hydrazide (**2**) on treatment with cyanogenbromide gave 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives which were condensed with different acid chlorides to get 2-benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4**) (Table 1). The structure of the product has been characterised by ir and nmr spectral data (Tables 2 and 3).